
BASUG LAW JOURNAL

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10492922>

WAQF (CHARITABLE TRUST): A PANACEA FOR THE EFFECTIVE POVERTY ERADICATION AND PROMOTING AN IDEAL SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

Poverty is one of the most profound problems being grappled with. It is contributing immensely to the erosion and undermining of the foundation of peaceful co-existence and sustainable national development across the globe. As such, poverty eradication is seen as a necessity especially in African countries which are characterized by high incidences of poverty and insecurity. This paper is aimed at addressing the question whether or not effective administration of WAQF property may play developmental role in society towards human social welfare? The paper adopts doctrinal research method where books, journals and articles as well as other relevant published materials are reviewed and critically analyzed. In its conclusion, the paper recommends solutions and strategies on how effective WAQF institutions will contribute in tackling poverty and insecurity and promote an ideal society. This research also found that properly managed Waqf is a means of poverty amelioration.

Keywords: Insecurity, Waqf, Poverty, Development.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

As a nation, Nigeria is passing through yet another moment with different challenges. These challenges are not unconnected with the rising of poverty level in all the regions of the country which resulted in nationwide insecurity. In short, there is no part of the country that has not experienced full blown conflicts in the recent times. In fact, in all the regions of the country, there are violent conflicts going on or one has just subsided or one is about to erupt¹.

Naturally, the citizens now live in perpetual fear and anxiety about their wellbeing. In other words, insecurity has created a febrile atmosphere, worsened by abject poverty and unemployment. These two factors have further compounded the fragile security condition of the country. Thus, the focus of this paper is to exploit other necessary measures to address these challenges, or at least reduce it to the barest minimum before it further escalates to another point. This paper further argues that, to achieve that, it becomes necessary to utilize all opportunities, to create human development through education and employment. This will no doubt de-escalate the situation.

The current challenges have manifestly, established that the government alone cannot effectively tackle and successfully address the problems of poverty and unemployment which are crucial to solving the present insecurity problem. It is important to point out here that, the present government has initiated, at different times, various intervention policies to tackle the issue of poverty, but to no avail². This is because these policies no matter how well planned, it could be difficult to tackle the problems due to the inconsistency in government policies, poor implementation of the policies as well as the high level of

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¹ Olayinka Akanle, "Youth Restiveness, National Security and development in Nigeria" Insecurity and Society in Nigeria, Ibadan university Press 2019 P..

² For instance, in 2000 Poverty Alliviation Programme (PAP), National Poverty Eradication Programma (NAPEP) in 2001 again, in 2004 the Federal Government launched the NEEDS programme later, Re-Investment and Empowerment Programme (SURE-P) and in recent item the government introduced the National Social Investment Programme (NISP). All these are Platforms for youth empowerment in Nigeria.

corrupt practices by those administering the policies. Poverty is a global problem and its eradication has received attention from national and international communities as well as Islamic and Conventional Institutions.

Poverty refers to the condition of life that is characterized by Hunger, Disease, Squalor, Mal-nutrition, Insecurity, Mental and Physical distress³. The world is predominantly made up of developing countries which the majority of the population suffer from poverty only few live in relative comfort. There are number of approaches to eradicate poverty. One of the most effective approaches to the poverty eradication is the act of giving *Sadaqah* (Charity Giving) and the most lasting of which is the *Sadaqatul Jariyah* (the perpetual charity) and one of the examples of this type of charity is the institution of *Waqf*. The role of *Waqf* in eradicating poverty is well pronounced, because it has done a lot in changing the life of people in terms of education, health services, mosques building and providing job opportunities. However, the problem is that recently there are element of corruption and mismanagement which hindered the impact of *WAQF* on the poor.

Thus, this paper examines the institutional framework of *WAQF* and issues related to the implementation of poverty eradication through *WAQF*. Accordingly, the paper adopts Doctrinal methodology of research whereby books, journals, articles and internet related materials will be reviewed and analyzed to demonstrate the impact of *WAQF* institution in poverty eradication.

Thus, this is an issue that requires a multidimensional response in order to be able to achieve the desired result. In other words, the issue requires serious and concerted effort by all and sundry. It is in this regard that this researcher decided to engage in this exercise. The paper will recommend strategies on how effective the management of *WAQF* institutions could help to offer lasting solution to tackle the problems of poverty and insecurity in Nigeria. Knowledge on the solutions that *Waqf* could offer to society in terms of creating wealth, education among other benefits form the nucleus of this research.

³ Umar Abubakar, "Waqf and Poverty Alleviation: A critical Review proceeding of 2nd International Conference, 28th - 29th April, 2015. Bench mark publishers Ltd. Karo (2015 P. 552).

Poverty and insecurity remain the general obstacle for the trajectory of social investment programmes in Nigeria.

And unless these issues are addressed, the problem of poverty and insecurity will never be adequately resolved as no nation can thrive with insecurity⁴.

2.0 CONCEPTUAL EXPLANATION OF *WAQF*

Waqf means a foundation of a charitable nature. It has been interpreted as; *an instance of 'Hubus' which means the giving or donation of the usufruct of a property which is in the entire or exclusive possession of the founder or donor for such a period as the property may remain in existence*⁵. While ownership of the *Waqf* property was thereby relinquished by the founder, it was not acquired by any other person, rather it was arrested or detained⁶. In other words, profit is appropriated for the good of mankind.

According to Magda et al, *Waqf* referred to a financial charitable act established by withholding immovable and movable properties to perpetually spend its revenue to fulfil public or family needs, based on the preference and conditions set by the founder⁷.

Under *Waqf*, the property is reserved and its usufruct appropriated for the benefit of specific individuals or for a general charitable purpose, the corpus becomes inalienable estates for life in favour of successive beneficiaries who can be created without regard to the law of inheritance or the right of the heirs; and continuity is secured by the successive appointment of trustees or *mutawallis*⁸. Three (3) basic principles govern the *Waqf*: the trust is required to be irrevocable, perpetual, and inalienable⁹. Thus, once a property is declared *Waqf* by its owner, the trust thereby created is irrevocable¹⁰.

⁴ Abu Hassan M. Sadeq

⁵ See Unguwar Garji v. Unguwar Garji (2014) 2 SCLR (Part II)

⁶ Yahaya Y. Bambale, "Islamic Law of Commercial and Industrials" Malta House Press Limited pg. 93

⁷ Magda M. I., Dafterda, H., Cizakca, M., Alhabshi, S.O., Razak, S. H., Sadr, S. K., & Obaidullah, M., "Financing the development of old Waqf Properties: classical Principles and Innovative Practices Around the World" US: Palgrave Macmillian 2016

⁸ Cattani, "the law of Waqf" in Law in the Middle East 203, 212 (1958)

⁹ Monica Op cit

¹⁰ Ibid

However, in some instances, the owner (*Waqif*) could retain certain rights as to its administration, but the endowment itself is invalid unless it is made irrevocable¹¹ and the waqif is bound by the terms of the *Waqf* documents. Likewise, the creation of the *Waqf* cannot be made subject to the actions of any third party, nor is a conventional option clause permissible¹².

Thus, the *Waqf* must also be made perpetual although the specific object of the trust need not to have been made permanent, rather, the requirement of perpetually referred to the dedication of the income of the *Waqf* to charitable purpose. If for instance, due to some other developments, the specific purpose for which the trust was created ceases to exist, the income realized from the *Waqfis* to be applied to a similar charitable object.

In the same vein, property (*Waqf*) is not transferrable and could not be the subject of any sale, disposition, mortgage, gift, inheritance, attachment or any alienation whatsoever. The above conditions relate only to the *Waqf* property.

Waqfis of two kinds; *Waqfal-ahli* (Family *Waqf*) and *Waqfal-khayri* (Welfare *Waqf*).

Waqfal-ahli or Family *Waqfis* created for the security and welfare of the family of the Waqif (Founder) and his close relatives. The aim is to ensure that it provide for their needs throughout their life time. After their death, it will automatically revert to the welfare of the poor people.

On the other hand, *Waqfal-khayri* otherwise known as welfare *Waqf*, is created to take care of the need of orphans, destitute, blind people and the handicapped. In the same vein, it can be created for the maintenance of Mosques, schools, hospitals, graveyards and other places of public welfare¹³.

¹¹ Maksifi, the guide of law in Medieval Legal History.....

¹² Ibid - An option clause... (N 26)

¹³ Abdulrahman I. Doi, "Shariah: The Islamic Law"

It is essential that the founder (*waqif*), must be in full possession of his physical and mental faculties, mature and free man¹⁴. He must also be the legal owner of the property declared to *Waqf* and it must yield income¹⁵. It can be made of both movable and immovable property.

3.0 THE ORIGIN AND LEGAL BASIS OF *WAQF*

Waqf traced its origin in the Hadith of the Holy Prophet Muhammad (pbuh). On the authority of Ibn Umar, who reported that Caliph Umar (may Allah be pleased with him) said to the prophet (pbuh) thus:

O Messenger of Allah, I acquired a land at Khaibar which I price highly, so what do you enjoin me about it? The Prophet replied; if you like, you can give the land as endowment and give its fruit in charity, on condition that the land and trees will neither be sold nor given as gift, nor be inherited or bequeathed.

Pursuant to the advice, Umar endowed it for the poor, for his Kith and Kin, for the emancipation of slaves, for the cause of Allah, for travelers in the way of Allah and for guests¹⁶.

Accordingly, *Waqf* is a trust aimed at bringing social services for a particular period to its beneficiaries. It funds these social services from the income generated and are forever inalienable. The social services provided here include building schools, libraries, hospitals, roads, bridges¹⁷ and scientific research. That is why the Prophet (pbuh) enjoined all the rich among his companions to give endowment¹⁸.

Waqf has been in existence since the pre-Islamic era up to the 19th century. It was estimated that *Waqf* properties in terms of agricultural land, in certain Muslim communities like Turkey (*Ottoman caliphate*), Egypt, Syria and Marocco were up to more than two third of the total land. These properties were used to address the economic problems of their people

¹⁴ Prophet Muhammed (Pbuh) was reported to have said that pen is lifted upon three categories of people: A minor until he attains majority, an insane person until he regains sanity and a drunkard until he becomes sober. Thus, any act done within this period is legally ineffective.

¹⁵ Heffing in Monica Op Cit.

¹⁶ Sahih Muslim: Book 13, No. 4006

¹⁷ Fahad Mohammed Al-Abdulmenem, *Waqf in Islamic Legall system and trust system in the United Kingdom. A comparative study* J.L.P.G. 61

¹⁸ Muslim, Bn Al-hajjaj Bn Muslim (n.d) Sahih Muslim Matba'ah Isa al-babu Al Halabi, Cairo Vol. 6.87

by reallocating such resources from existing consumption to invest in areas that create revenues for future consumption of their people¹⁹.

4.0 UNEMPLOYMENT AND POVERTY AS CAUSES OF INSECURITY

Unemployment causes poverty and extreme poverty leads to crimes which give rise to insecurity. Poverty is a situation in which people live below a defined standard of living due to little or no income, so that individuals and nations as classified and identified as poor while unemployment is defined as when people are not engaged in meaningful work and are lacking in basic need of life²⁰.

The causes of crime have been a subject of debate by scholars. Some argued that the main causes can be historical, cultural, religious, economic, social and psychological²¹. Suffice to say, many reasons can be attributed to insecurity in any given nation depending on its peculiarities. That notwithstanding among the multitude of causes that may lead a person to resort to committing crime, there is none that conclusively link a sole cause to it. Ethnicity, nationalism, poverty and economic disadvantage, globalization (non) democracy, disaffected intelligence, arguments confirming a possible existing link, as well as reservation against casual relation²².

The abject poverty that has ravaged Nigeria is not a new trend. It has been with us for long and has attended such a recurring phenomenon the chain of which the leaders appear incapable of breaking or indeed unwilling to break²³. Poverty got to that alarming state because of the insatiable and unholy desire by some few political power holders over the years, to join the category of wealthy super-rich persons at the expense of those who they claimed to govern. Those who help them achieve this seat of political power. It is pertinent to state that despite the utter insincerity on the part of the elite in terms of embezzling of the state resources, there has never been any conscious attempt at the re-structuring of

¹⁹ Muhammed Hydara, 'An Integrative Model of Waqf, Sadaqah and Takaful for Poverty Alleviation through Empowering Women Farmers in Rural Gambia' *Journal of Islamic Finance*, Vol. 9 No. 2 2020.

²⁰ Nasiru Zubairu. "Rising insecurity in Nigeria: Causes and Solution" *Journal of Studies in Social Science*. V.19 2020 4.

²¹ Terrorism, A growing challenges forming nation. M.O Edeko & Chinwe Okoli k. (2013) JPL V01. 1 No. 1

²² C. Maria Keet "Causes of terrorism", <http://www.mwtwck.org/causesterrorism.html> accessed in Ibid.

²³ Poverty, Law and justice.

the society in to order to eliminate poverty as much as possible; one of the reasons for this reckless attitude is because each set of politicians has thought that its first paramount duty after attaining to the seat of power, was to enrich its members and their supporters at the expense of the vast poor and to care for the poor only to the extent of what is left over²⁴.

Conversely, there is no gain saying that as long as there is such a disparity in the distribution of wealth within the society as to make some live below the starvation level, there will be no hope for better and more prosperous society. Going forward, it is evident that majority of those who could be said to be wealthy did not accumulate their wealth from their own labour and sweat. In other words, they join that category owing to their political appointment, also successive regimes from independence to date, continue to produce more super-rich persons as well as more super-poor persons in large numbers²⁵.

Unemployment on the other hand, is very high in Nigeria. Restiveness has become so normal that absence of it is abnormal in Nigeria from the Niger Delta conflict to the *Ordua* in the West to the Movement or the Sovereign State of Biafra (*MASSOB*) in the East and recently, Boko Haram, banditry and cattle rustling in the North. Restiveness and its consequences are endemic in the country²⁶.

The youths form the basic and major armies perpetrating and driving conflict across the country. They are vulnerable or easily recruited to perpetuate conflict because of their disadvantaged situation. They are made to confront many challenges that are not their making. Therefore, these conflicts are mostly promoted by youths. The youths form a major proportion of the Nigerian populations²⁷. They are the force that drive the country and the barometer with which the dimension of the development occurrences in the country can be gauged²⁸.

Naturally, these youths have their dreams and aspirations, once their effort is frustrated or endangered they explore other options to achieve a survival. In that, they become

²⁴ *ibid*

²⁵ *ibid*

²⁶ Poverty, law and justice

²⁷ Olayinka Op:Cit

²⁸ *ibid*

potential recruits by criminals. Their ambitions, dreams, ideas, goals and energy which ordinarily supposed to be an asset for the country will become an agent of destructions.

In order to avoid all these tendencies and to maintain an ideal state, there must be a just society, it must be organized in such a way as to make each man the keeper of every other man. And one method of effectuating that organization is the reduction of poverty by creating employment to the citizens.

Waqf, in the opinion of this writer, is one of the ways to achieve that. The state must, at all times, employ all avenues in discharging the pressing duty of the state to provide for the minimum standard of living for its citizens, and for their happiness through social justice. Understandably, the issue is quite cumbersome, hence the need to encourage and sensitize other wealthy citizens to join the force. More so, insecurity affects every body.

As it is now, the social relation that exist between the political class and average citizens is that of mistrust and distrust, as the citizens see the political class as nonchalant to their plights. The unemployment rate in Nigeria increases by the day. In other words, there is no gainsaying that Nigeria is among the nations with highest level of unemployment. This has made Nigerians to experience high level of poverty since the immediate and the most practical outcome of unemployment is poverty and systematic disempowerment of all geo-political zones.

This explains the social reality and social psychology of poverty as the thing of the mind with huge practical capacity to influence actions negatively. It is possible to observe a strong link between poverty and perpetration and involvement in restiveness and conflict.²⁹ For instance, in the North, it has the most predominance of poverty, when one considers the fact that the Northern Nigeria is the epicenter of the Boko Haram insurgency and most recently the cases of kidnapping, banditry and cattle rustling.

The Government, both at the state and federal levels, appeared indifferent and therefore failed to commit adequate effort to understand the causes of these conflict situations and

²⁹ Olayinka Akanle - Op:Cit

proffer lasting solutions or perhaps, deliberately chose to ignore that so that the youths can be used to pursue political goals.

There must be a well and genuine effort from the government and the citizens to decisively address this issue in order to bring it to an end and to avoid its recurrence. Failure to take such a giant move in resolving this lingering problem will keep fermenting and brewing grievances until it culminates to another violent circle³⁰.

One can safely argue that charitable *Waqf* is purposely introduced to cater for cases of poverty and other social menace in the society. It is established to eliminate poverty and for the creation of social service facilities such as schools, libraries, hospitals, roads, bridges etc. for the benefit of the downtrodden in the society³¹. Being embedded in religion, many scholars trust that the institution of *Waqf* has its beginning in the *Qur'an* that point out the formation of religions or charitable foundations. It is submitted that a *Waqf* is a form of charity for the sake of Allah which is documented by law because of its influence on sustainable development.³²

It is an elementary principle of Islam that the rich are enjoined to help the needy, hence the doctrine of *Waqf*. In fact, the poor section of the society is entitled to share in their wealth. To achieve this, Allah (S.W.A) institutionalized the system of *Zakkat*. The whole essence of this is to relieve poverty³³.

Thus, Islam lays great emphasis on the relief of poverty by the rich. To this end, the Holy Qur'an declared thus:

*"The poor and the unfortunate have a right in their (the rich people's) property"*³⁴.

In effect, it is a duty of the rich and prosperous individuals to take part in the economic uplift of the poor. The idea is to have a peaceful society and to strengthen the kinships. In another

³⁰ Egbue Ngozi G., e etal

³¹ Fahad Mohammed Alabdulmenem "Waqf in Islamic Legal system in the United Kingdom: A Comparative Study", journal of law, policy and globalization Vol. 61, 2017.

³² ibid

³³ Abdulrahman I. Doi, "Shariah: The Islamic Law"

³⁴ 51:19

verse, the Holy Qur'an criticize and condemn all those well-meaning individuals who only engage in trade activities without giving any regard to the poor in terms of charity. It says:

"And those who go on hoarding gold and silver and do not spend it in the way of Allah, give them warning of a great punishment"³⁵.

It can easily be understood from the above verse that wealthy individuals must understand that the less privileged people are also entitled to a share from their wealth and not to be reserved for them and their families only. One of the easiest way to discharge this obligation is through the establishment of *waqaf*.

It is pertinent to state that this duty is not only discharged by payment of Zakat, admittedly, it is the major way but still there are some other significant avenues which one can earn Allah's treasures. In fact, the Prophet (PBUH), in a Hadith related by Safwan Ibn Salim, said:

"A man who helps and spends his time and money in looking after widows and the poor, holds the same position in the eyes of Allah as one who fight in the Holy war or fast every day and prays the whole night over a number of years"³⁶.

Similarly, in another hadith, Anas related that the prophet (PBUH) said:

"If any Muslim plants something or sows seed from which a man, a bird or an animal eats, it counts as charity from him"³⁷.

The prophet (PBUH) has not made any distinction in the Tradition between Muslims and non-Muslims. This is because the whole idea is to encourage doing good by helping the needy and less privileged. However, establishment of philanthropic Waqf is only voluntary and not an obligation like the payment of Zakat

BENEFITS OF WAQF

³⁵ Qur'an Chapter 9 Verse 3 (1998). A. Yusuf Ali Modern English translation of the Qur'an meaning and commentary, Manar int'l. cooperation.

³⁶ Sahih Bukhari, M. Muhsin Khan, (2005) International University of Malay, at www.iium.edu.my/hadith accessed on 16th August, 2023

³⁷ Sahih Bukhari and Muslim, M. Muhsin Khan, (2005) International University of Malay, at www.iium.edu.my/hadith accessed on 16th August, 2023.

It is instrumental to state that one of the important benefits of *Waqf* is that it will create wealth, enhance the life chance of the people, build human capital and promote equality of opportunity. *Waqf* will help catalyze economic recovery and growth. It will comprehensively mitigate insurgency and banditry and revive socio-economic activities.

Thus, identifying this area as untapped potential represents an opportunity for new reforms that can sustain Nigeria as a peaceful ground and will drastically reduce insecurity. This can be achieved by making contribution toward the objective of ending extreme poverty and promoting shared prosperity.

It is pertinent to observe that going through the history, it has been shown that *Waqf* has played an instrumental role in both socio-economic development and the eradication of poverty for over 1,400 years throughout Islamic history.³⁸ These service include: provision of education, health care, and infrastructural development as well as socio-economic assistance to the poor and vulnerable. Further, *Waqf* institutions have also supported improvements in income and wealth equality as affluent individuals provide resources for the benefit of the needy.³⁹

5.0 CONCLUSION

In the pursuit to achieve a peaceful, secured and an ideal society, it would require that policy makers go beyond military approach or using violence to stem the tide of violence. There is need to come up with ideas that will stimulate policy debate, identify potential challenges and devise means of addressing the challenges. This remains the key to foster and develop economy, peace, security and stability. *Waqf* is an imperative socio-economic instrument, which if implemented appropriately, can drastically reduce the problem of poverty, restiveness and will promote job creation and improve the living standard of the people. It represents one of the untapped potential instruments which provide an opportunity for new reforms that will provide and sustain a peaceful and secured environment.

³⁸ Mohammed Rozani Osman and Ahmad Hafiz Abdul-aziz, "Waqf: providing alternative finance for sustainable Development". Development digest issue 08-April-2020. Available at bit.ly/waqfsolutionsmywb.

³⁹ Ibid